

Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on the Socio-economic Scenario of a Typical Rural Village of Andhra Pradesh, India

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Abstract— The impact of COVID-19 on socio-economic landscape has been significant across the globe. In India, the pandemic has caused widened inequality, education disruption, job losses, income decline, and GDP contraction. In this context, the present study was taken up to assess the impact of COVID-19 pandemic on the socio-economic scenario of a typical village - Mylavaram - located in state of Andhra Pradesh state, India. Field data was collected using open source Kobocollect mobile app. 55% of the total population were interviewed to collect data related their socio-economic conditions, health details and COVID-19 details. The study indicates - income loss, increase in the cost of living and disruption of education were significantly impacted due to COVID pandemic. Majority of the people were not satisfied with the Government response in controlling the pandemic, the available government and private medical facilities. A small segment of people were satisfied with the vaccination drive.

Keywords— COVID-19 Pandemic, Socio-economic Survey, COVID Statistics, Health care facilities, Income loss, SARS-CoV-2

I. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic, caused by the coronavirus SARS-CoV-2, emerged in late 2019 and had rapidly escalated into a global pandemic by early 2020. The pandemic had far-reaching consequences, affecting public health, economies, and societies worldwide. To curb the spread of the virus, Governments implemented lockdowns, travel restrictions, and social distancing measures. Healthcare systems worldwide faced unprecedented challenges, including shortages of medical supplies, hospital beds, and healthcare workers [1]. The pandemic has significantly impacted India's socio-economic scenario across various dimensions. India has experienced a severe economic downturn due to the pandemic. The country's GDP contracted by 7.3% in the fiscal year 2020-21, marking the first contraction in four decades [2]. The pandemic has led to widespread job losses and reduced incomes, particularly affecting informal and migrant workers. According to the Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE), India's unemployment rate surged to historic highs during the lockdown periods in 2020 [3]. India's healthcare system faced immense pressure with a surge in COVID-19 cases. Hospitals in several states were overwhelmed, highlighting gaps in healthcare infrastructure and resources [4].

In India, the pandemic has exacerbated the existing socio-economic inequalities significantly. Vulnerable populations, including low-income households, informal workers, and marginalized communities, faced disproportionate impacts in terms of health outcomes and economic vulnerabilities [5]. School closures have disrupted education for millions of students across India, causing disparities in access to online learning and impacting learning outcomes, particularly for children from economically disadvantaged backgrounds [6]. Silver lining during these challenging times was the unprecedented digital adoption in India across sectors such as e-commerce, telemedicine, and remote work. This shift underscored both opportunities and challenges in bridging digital divides and enhancing digital infrastructure [7]. The Indian government implemented various fiscal stimulus measures and relief

packages to mitigate the socio-economic impact of the pandemic. These included direct cash transfers, free food grains, and credit support for businesses [8].

In the above context, the present study was envisaged to study in detail the impact and consequences of COVID-19 pandemic on the socio-economic fabric at the grass roots level. Hence, Mylavaram, a typical rural village of Andhra Pradesh, was chosen for the study.

II. STUDY AREA

The study area, Mylavaram is located at 16.7833°N 80.6333°E belonging to the NTR district, formerly Krishna District of Andhra Pradesh, India (Fig. 1). As per 2011 Census data, Mylavaram has 5,669 households with total population of 21,763 and density of 1,477. Average sex ratio of Mylavaram village is 1016 which is higher than Andhra Pradesh state average of 993. The literacy rate is 76.49%, higher when compared to 67.02% of Andhra Pradesh [9].

Fig.1 Location of Mylavaram Village

III. METHODOLOGY

Questionnaire for household survey was prepared after consulting the GIS database experts, local health officials, Mandal Revenue Officer (MRO) and other village officers. The questionnaire has three major categories: (i) General health profile & COVID details (ii) socio-economic details and (iii) infrastructure details.

General health profile & COVID details comprises the number of people in the house, number of times they are infected with COVID, vaccination taken, type of vaccine and medications taken. *Socio-economic details* include the type of house, households, source of income, drinking water and sanitation facilities, impact of COVID pandemic on the economic situation, opinion about the Government's approach in handling the pandemic. *Infrastructure details* include schools, government offices, bus stops, cinema halls, commercial complexes, hotels and other important features in the village, where possible conglomeration of public is possible and hence the possible spread of contagious diseases.

Necessary permissions were obtained from the *Grama-ward Sachivalayam* (local legislative office, an initiative taken by the Government of Andhra Pradesh) and MRO office of Mylavaram Mandal for taking up the house-hold and infrastructure survey.

Field Data Collection

Field surveyors were trained and deployed to collect details from individuals through door-to-door survey based on personal interview using KoboCollect android app. The KoboCollect app is based on the open source ODK Collect app and is used for primary data collection in humanitarian emergencies and other challenging field environments [10]. This app has the facility to enter data from interviews or other primary data – online or offline. It also has the feature to collect the geographic coordinates of the house where the survey is conducted. The app also records the entire interview to facilitate quality control and assessment. Field data is updated directly through cloud interface.

IV. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

In Mylavaram village, 3,384 households comprising of 12,043 individuals (55% of the total population as per Census 2011 data) were interviewed to collect COVID-19 related information and their socio-economic conditions. The household and village level survey were conducted during the months of March and April 2022.

As on April 2022, based on the voluntary disclosure, there were 615 (5.1%) COVID confirmed cases, 586 (4.9%) recovered cases and 29 (0.2%) were dead due to COVID pandemic. Most of the confirmed COVID-19 cases were house wives followed by daily wage labour (Fig 2).

Fig.2 Details of COVID-19 affected cases in Mylavaram

Fig.2 indicates 8,391 (70%) respondents were vaccinated with Dose 1 and 2; 222 (2%) have confirmed they had booster dose, 679 (6%) had only one dose of vaccine, and 2,751 (23%) are not vaccinated. 66% were vaccinated with Covishield vaccine and 8% with Covaxin.

The various socio-economic factors, the opinion of respondents about the government initiatives taken to curb the pandemic, COVID-19 medical treatment availed and the hospitals where they were treated have been discussed below.

A. Socio-economic Factors

Income loss and increase in the cost of living are the main aspects significantly impacted due to COVID-19 pandemic (Fig. 3) followed by education and increase of hospital expenses, death of family members, loss of jobs and business opportunities.

Fig.3 Impacts of COVID-19 in Mylavaram

The pandemic has caused income loss to many people in Mylavaram. It can be understood from Fig. 4 that, in Mylavaram village, as many as 46% respondents claimed that they have lost their income by more than 25%. While 2% respondents have lost income in the range of 75% to 100%, 13% respondents lost their income in the range of 50%-75%. Nearly 31% respondents have lost income in the range of 25 to 50% while 54% respondents have lost income in the range of 0-25%.

Fig.4 Income affected people due to COVID-19 in Mylavaram

B. Government Initiatives

The residents of Mylavaram village were not very happy with the government initiatives in controlling the pandemic (Refer Fig.5). Nearly 24% were satisfied with the vaccination drive. 20% respondents felt the lock-down was unnecessary. In general, the respondents were not satisfied with both the government and private and medical facilities. The respondents are however not quite happy with the availability of medical facilities, both the public or private facilities and vaccination drive to combat COVID-19 pandemic.

C. COVID-19 Treatment

In Mylavaram, among the COVID infected patients, 30% have undergone treatment at hospital, 23% got treatment at home based on doctor advise, 21% have not taken any treatment, 27% have used Government sponsored COVID-kit, 7% have taken over-the-counter medicines from medical shops, and 1% have taken

medicines based on friends' advice. This indicates that, majority of the villagers have undergone treatment to the pandemic.

Fig.5 Responses of Villages to the actions taken by the Government to contain COVID-19 pandemic

D. Government vs Private Hospital

As many as 64% respondents have undergone treatment for COVID-19 at private hospital and 36% at government hospital. This indicates people have preferred private medical care over the government medical care.

E. Location of Hospitals Preferred for Treatment

Majority of the respondents in the village i.e., 58%, have undergone treatment at Vijayawada, which is the nearest available centre for medical care, while 13% undergone treatment at Mylavaram. Interestingly, 4% have visited Hyderabad which is nearly 280 Km away but is known to have better Medical facilities, and remaining followed their best available practices.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The present study indicates income loss, increased cost of living and education were severely affected due to the COVID-19 pandemic. People were not satisfied with the Government response in controlling the pandemic and the provision of medical facilities in both the public and private hospitals. A small segment of people were satisfied with the vaccination drive.

The COVID-19 pandemic has struck us hard - giving us no breathing space and time to fight it. The potential for future pandemics remains high due to several emerging and re-emerging pathogens [11]. It's time we learn from the challenges of COVID-19 and be prepared for the future pandemics.

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REFERENCES

- [1] WHO. (2020) WHO Website. Available at: <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019>
- [2] Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (2021). MOSPI Website. Available at: <https://mospi.gov.in/>
- [3] CMIE. (2021). Available at: <https://www.cmie.com/>.
- [4] The Lancet. (2021) "India's COVID-19 emergency," *The Lancet*, 397 (10286), 1683.
- [5] Oxfam India. (2021) Oxfam Website. Available at: <https://www.oxfamindia.org/>
- [6] UNESCO. (2021). UNESCO Website. Available at: <https://en.unesco.org/covid19/educationresponse>
- [7] NASSCOM. (2021).NASSCOM Website Available at: <https://nasscom.in/>
- [8] Ministry of Finance, Government of India. (2021) Indian Government Website. Available at: <https://www.indiabudget.gov.in/economicssurvey/>
- [9] Census. (2011). Census of India Website. Available at: <https://censusindia.gov.in/census.website>
- [10] ODK. (2024). ODK Website. Available at: <https://getodk.org>
- [11] Gavi (2024). GAVI Website. Available at: <https://www.gavi.org/vaccineswork/10-infectious-diseases-could-be-next-pandemic>